

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *Technology has brought significant changes to all aspects of life in the 21st century. New technology improved the existing educational system and gave it a new direction. Education, including English, has undergone numerous modifications. The teaching of English has evolved significantly, with teachers and learners increasingly relying on cutting-edge technology to enhance learning experiences. In the modern world, the teachers of English have been using a variety of teaching materials in order to satisfy the needs and interests of the learners. In this process, they also go for the authentic materials in order to improve the standards of the learners and to develop their learners' language skills enormously in the regular English classrooms.*

Key words: *authentic materials, vocabulary, TV shows, podcasts, websites, videos and so on.*

Expanding one's vocabulary is essential in the area of language since words aid language users in expressing thoughts, ideas, or desired meanings. People cannot communicate or understand one another without a sufficient vocabulary. When communicating, using language without grammar yields very little; however, if language users lack vocabulary, nothing can be conveyed [5,168]. Furthermore, if language structure is considered metaphorically as the skeleton of the language, vocabulary is viewed metaphorically as the lifeblood and flesh [1,34]. As a result, having a sufficient or extensive vocabulary is necessary for meaningful conversation.

Furthermore, acquiring a sufficient vocabulary is critical for successful second language use when learning a language as a second or foreign language because language users will be unable to communicate effectively using the language's structures and functions without a large vocabulary [4,107]. As a result, speakers of a second language must learn and retain a large amount of vocabulary. This suggests that for EFL and ESL students, vocabulary development is critical for improving all language skills, including listening, speaking, reading, and writing [3,78].

Authentic resources show real-world examples of language in everyday contexts. They can be utilized to generate more interest in the learner. They might act as a reminder to learners that the target language is used by an entire population in their daily lives. Authentic materials can provide information about the target culture as well as its perspective on a particular subject or event. The rich language present in real sources provides learners with the necessary input for language acquisition.

According to Thornbury [5, 168] authentic materials are any educational materials that were not created with the intention of being used in a classroom. Therefore, Morrow's quotation from 1977 regarding authentic discourse is also quite relevant:

“...a stretch of real language, produced by a real speaker or writer for a real audience and designed to convey a real message of some sort.”

Authentic resources do not intentionally target any particular grammar, vocabulary, or learning objectives, nor have they been developed with second language learners in mind. Thus, the most authentic materials originate from reliable sources such as news organizations and podcasts, but they may also be found in menus, books, TV shows, photographs, novels, and

schedules for buses. Around the actual material, educators can develop dynamic and captivating lesson plans that are carefully adapted to the skill levels of their students.

These resources are incredibly effective tools for enhancing your students' learning for a number of strong reasons. Below is a list of the most significant benefits.

- Teachers might introduce material about current events and news in the area.
- As a result, learners may become more interested and engaged with authentic resources.
- Language learners require authentic resources as a vital source of high-quality input for language acquisition, and these materials' actual and rich language delivers just that.
- Teachers of languages might be encouraged to use more creative content in their lessons by using authentic materials.
- Authentic resources offer authentic instances of the language that is genuinely employed in daily interactions

Importantly, this argument highlights the most usually asserted disadvantage of using real materials in the classroom: that they are only appropriate for higher level pupils. But this is, of course, the entire purpose. [As the British Council suggests](#): *“Your text, written or recorded, is likely to be too hard, even, in some cases, for advanced students. The trick, regardless of the text used, is not to edit and grade the text, but to grade the task according to your students’ abilities.”*

In the realm of language learning, vocabulary acquisition plays a crucial role in enabling students to effectively communicate and comprehend a foreign language. While traditional vocabulary exercises have their merit, incorporating authentic materials into the learning process can significantly enhance students' vocabulary skills and overall language proficiency. Authentic materials refer to real-world texts, such as newspapers, magazines, websites, videos, and social media posts, that are created for native speakers of the target language. Vocabulary can be taught using a variety of ways, such as graphics, mime, word maps, vocabulary games, and dictionaries. In addition to the approaches previously discussed, teachers can use compelling objects, such as real things, to assist children understand terminology. Real materials are interesting and inspirational. Shrum and Glisan [3, 102] believe that authentic resources are an effective way to introduce and increase comprehension of genuine language, including culture. Shrum and Glisan argue that authentic resources are advantageous. Students will first get the opportunity to see language in action in the actual world. Furthermore, the resources might be seen as a valuable resource for learning about different cultures.

One of the key advantages of using authentic materials to improve students' vocabulary skills is the exposure to language as it is naturally used by native speakers. By engaging with authentic texts, students encounter vocabulary in context, gaining a deeper understanding of word meanings, usage, and collocations. This exposure helps students develop a more nuanced and authentic command of the language, enabling them to communicate more effectively in real-world situations. Moreover, authentic materials provide students with a window into the culture, customs, and current affairs of the target language community. This cultural immersion enhances students' language learning experience by making vocabulary acquisition more meaningful and relevant. For example, reading news articles in the target language not only exposes students to new vocabulary but also allows them to understand different perspectives on global events and issues. Incorporating authentic materials into vocabulary learning activities can make the process more engaging and motivating for students. Authentic texts are often more interesting and dynamic than traditional vocabulary lists or exercises, capturing students' attention and sparking their curiosity.

This increased engagement can lead to higher levels of student involvement and retention of vocabulary, as students are more likely to remember words encountered in meaningful and authentic contexts. To effectively utilize authentic materials for improving students' vocabulary skills, educators can design a variety of engaging activities. For instance, teachers can create vocabulary quizzes based on newspaper articles, ask students to watch and discuss videos in the target language, or assign projects that require students to analyze and present information from authentic sources. By integrating authentic materials into the curriculum, educators can create a rich language learning environment that promotes vocabulary growth and linguistic proficiency.

In conclusion, incorporating authentic materials into language learning can greatly benefit students' vocabulary skills by providing exposure to real-world language use, fostering cultural awareness, and increasing student engagement. By leveraging authentic texts in the classroom, educators can enhance the effectiveness of vocabulary instruction and empower students to develop a deeper and more authentic command of the target language.

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